

LOCAL EFFECTS ACROSS CORE JUNCTIONS IN SANDWICH PLATES

Ole T. Thomsen, Elena Bozhevolnaya, Arne Kildegaard and Vitaly Skvortsov *

*Institute of Mechanical Engineering, Aalborg University
Pontoppidanstraede 101, DK-9220 Aalborg, Denmark, www.ime.auc.dk
*State Marine Technical University of St.-Petersburg,
Leninski Prospect 101, 198262 St.-Petersburg, Russia*

SUMMARY: Sandwich beams and plates with symmetric faces and inclusion of cores of various elastic properties are investigated. Focus of presented theoretical and experimental studies is on the local effects that occur in the vicinity of intersections between cores of different stiffness in sandwich panels. These local effects manifest themselves by a significant rise of the bending stresses in the faces in the vicinity of the core junctions. Closed-form estimates of the stress/strain fields induced by local effects are presented for sandwich beams and panels loaded in cylindrical bending. The accuracy of the derived closed-form estimates is verified experimentally for the case of a sandwich beam in three-point bending.

KEYWORDS: sandwich plates, core junctions, stress concentrations, analytical modelling, experimental investigation.

NOTATION

b - beam/plate width;	l_1, l_2 - characteristic lengths of local effect;
c_1, c_2, c_3, c_4 - coefficients of distributions;	M - bending moment;
D - bending stiffness of sandwich beam/panel;	N - normal force;
D_f - bending stiffness of beam face;	Q - shear force;
E_{c1} - modulus of elasticity of a compliant core;	Q_0 - shear force at junction;
E_f - modulus of elasticity of the faces;	S - shear rigidity of sandwich panel;
E_{xf} - modulus of elasticity of the faces;	x - coordinate (origin at junction);
F - loading force;	$\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \beta_1, \beta_2$ - decay coefficients;
f_z, f_τ, f_σ - distribution functions;	ε_f - normal strain in face;
G_{c1}, G_{c2} - shear moduli of compliant and stiff cores;	μ - ratio of shear and bending stiffness;
g - ratio of shear moduli;	ν_c, ν_f - Poisson's ratio of core and faces;
h - total thickness of sandwich beam/plate;	σ_c - normal stress in core;
h_c, h_f - thickness of sandwich core and faces;	$\sigma_f^{top}, \sigma_f^{bot}$ - normal stress in faces;
k, k_σ - additional coefficients;	σ_0^{loc} - maximum local normal stress in faces;
L - length of sandwich beam;	τ_c - shear stress in core.

INTRODUCTION

Sandwich plates with composite face sheets are used successfully for many structural applications especially in transportation due to very high bending stiffness, high strength and high buckling resistance [1]-[3]. Purposeful and tailored design of light-weight structures compels sandwich components to have inclusions of various cores with dissimilar mechanical properties as well as insertions of different rigid inserts, which serve the purpose of enabling the assembly and attachment of additional components, devices etc.

Any discontinuity of the elastic properties at the junctions of various materials lead to the formation of boundary layers or local effects at the junctions [4]. These local effects manifest themselves by a significant rise of the bending stresses in the faces in the vicinity of the core junctions, and the peak

values of these local bending stresses may be comparable to or exceed the globally induced face bending stresses. This represents a considerable danger in relation to the structural integrity of the entire assembly, since sandwich structures are notoriously sensitive to failure caused by local bending effects induced in the vicinity of points of geometric, material and loading discontinuities. Simple analytical derivation of the stress distributions in sandwich beams with clamped edges (which to some extent are similar to rigid inserts) has been performed in classical monographs on sandwich structures [5]-[7]. There are a number of high-order theories, which describe the strain and stress states around rigid inserts, diaphragms and localised loads [8]-[12]. However, these models did not suggest closed-form analytical expressions for core junctions or rigid inserts, and no attempts have been made experimental verification of these type of local effects. The present paper introduces closed-form estimates of the face and core material strain and stress fields in the vicinity of core junctions in sandwich beams/plates. The accuracy of the derived closed-form estimates is verified experimentally for the case of a sandwich beam in three-point bending.

BRIEF OF THE THEORETICAL MODEL

A typical junction between two different cores in a sandwich panel with symmetrical faces is shown in Fig. 1, which also displays the adopted notation for geometry and material data of the sandwich constituents. The theoretical modelling of local effects induced near junctions between different core materials in sandwich panels was developed by Skvortsov and Thomsen in [13], to which the reader is referred for the details of the modelling. The model is based on a third-order shear plate theory (a classification due to Noor *et al* [14]), which is suitable for the analysis of sandwich panels in cylindrical bending with relatively thin and stiff faces, i.e. the following model constraints need to be fulfilled

$$h_f^2 \ll h_c^2 \quad \text{and} \quad E_f h_f \gg E_c h_c \quad (1)$$

It was shown by Skvortsov [15] that for sandwich structures that satisfy the inequalities (1) two types of local effects with typical decay lengths l_1 and l_2 (symmetric and anti-symmetric deformation) of the boundary effects exist

$$l_1 \approx \left(\frac{E_f h_f^3 h_c}{6G_c (h_c + h_f)^2} \right)^{1/2}, \quad l_2 \approx \left(\frac{E_f h_f^3 h_c}{6E_c} \right)^{1/4} \quad (2)$$

These characteristic lengths describe the decay of the local disturbances. They are the only boundary layers that may be sufficiently larger than the beam/panel total thickness h . Therefore l_1 and l_2 are expected to be negligible in comparison with the characteristic length L of a relatively thin sandwich beam/plate, i.e.

$$l_1, l_2 \ll L \quad \text{and} \quad h_f, h_c \ll L \quad (3)$$

Figure 1. An element of a sandwich beam/plate where two different cores materials adjoin. The global internal resultants in the beam are indicated at the right cross-section: N – normal force, Q – shear force and M – bending moment.

The shear stiffness S and the bending stiffness D of the entire sandwich assembly, and the bending stiffness D_f of the sandwich faces are defined as follows

$$S = \frac{G_c (h_f + h_c)^2}{h_c}, \quad D = \frac{E_{xf} h_f (h_f + h_c)^2}{2}, \quad D_f = \frac{E_{xf} h_f^3}{6} \quad (4)$$

where $E_{xf} = E_f$ for plane stress, and $E_{xf} = E_f / (1 - \nu^2)$ for plane strain conditions.

Two principal model parameters are of special importance. The first important model parameter is the ratio g of the shear moduli of the adjoining core materials

$$g = \sqrt{\frac{G_{c1}}{G_{c2}}} \quad (5)$$

The second important model parameter is the decay parameter μ that characterizes the extension of the local effects (the bending boundary layer)

$$\mu = \sqrt{k \frac{G_{c1} h_c (h_c + h_f)^2}{E_f h_f^3}}, \quad k = \frac{1 - \nu_f}{4} \quad \text{for plane stress} \quad (6)$$

$$k = \frac{1 - 2\nu_f}{4(1 - \nu_f)} \quad \text{for plane strain}$$

Normal stresses in the faces: It was shown in [13] that, in absence of distributed surface and axial loads, local bending of the sandwich faces take place due to the presence of a shear stress resultant Q_0 at the junction. The maximum local bending stress is proportional to the shear stress resultant

$$\sigma_0^{loc} = Q_0 \sqrt{\frac{3E_f}{2G_{c1} h_f h_c}} (1 - g) k_\sigma \quad (7)$$

where k_σ is an implicit function, which with a high accuracy is approximated as

$$k_\sigma = \frac{\sqrt{1 + 2\mu}}{1 + \mu(1 + g^{1/4})}$$

The maximum stress in the faces occurs in the near vicinity of the junction some distance into the stiffer core. The variation of the local bending stress $\sigma_f^{loc}(x)$ in the vicinity of the junction located at $x=0$ is defined by a function f_σ

$$\sigma_f^{loc}(x) = \sigma_0^{loc} f_\sigma$$

$$f_\sigma = \frac{c_1 \alpha_1 e^{-\alpha_1 x} + c_2 \beta_1 e^{-\beta_1 x}}{c_1 \alpha_1 + c_2 \beta_1}, \quad x > 0 \quad (8)$$

$$f_\sigma = \frac{c_3 \alpha_2 e^{+\alpha_2 x} + c_4 \beta_2 e^{+\beta_2 x}}{c_3 \alpha_2 + c_4 \beta_2}, \quad x < 0$$

where

$$\alpha_1 = \sqrt{\frac{6}{k} \frac{\sqrt{1+2\mu} + \sqrt{1-2\mu}}{2} \frac{1}{h_c}}, \quad \alpha_2 = \sqrt{\frac{6}{k} \frac{\sqrt{1+2\mu/g} + \sqrt{1-2\mu/g}}{2} \frac{1}{h_c}} \quad (9)$$

$$\beta_1 = \sqrt{\frac{6}{k} \frac{\sqrt{1+2\mu} - \sqrt{1-2\mu}}{2} \frac{1}{h_c}}, \quad \beta_2 = \sqrt{\frac{6}{k} \frac{\sqrt{1+2\mu/g} - \sqrt{1-2\mu/g}}{2} \frac{1}{h_c}}$$

and the coefficients c_1, c_2, c_3, c_4 of the distribution function (or decay function) f_σ are found by solving a set of linear algebraic equations, which is obtained by enforcing continuity of all internal resultants across the core junction

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & -g^2 & -g^2 \\ \alpha_1 & \beta_1 & g^2 \alpha_2 & g^2 \beta_2 \\ \alpha_1^2 & \beta_1^2 & -g^2 \alpha_2^2 & -g^2 \beta_2^2 \\ \alpha_1^3 & \beta_1^3 & g^4 \alpha_2^3 & g^4 \beta_2^3 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} c_1 \\ c_2 \\ c_3 \\ c_4 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} g^2 - 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (10)$$

The character of the decay function f_σ is such that the local bending stresses vanish at a certain distance from the junction. It is important to realize that the local bending stressed induced by the internal shear force is an additional stress in the faces, which has to be superimposed to the bending stresses σ_M^{top} and σ_M^{bot} that may exist in the faces due to presence of an overall bending moment $M(x)$. Thus, the net stresses at the upper (top) and lower (bottom) faces of the sandwich read

$$\sigma_f^{top} = \sigma_M^{top} \pm \sigma_{max}^{loc}, \quad \sigma_f^{bot} = \sigma_M^{bot} \pm \sigma_{max}^{loc} \quad (11)$$

where $\sigma_M^{top} = -\sigma_M^{bot} = M \frac{(h_c + 2h_f)}{h_f(h_c + h_f)^2}$, and + and - correspond to the upper and lower fibres

of each face, respectively. The direction of the positive normal stresses corresponds to the sign convention displayed in Fig. 1.

Shear and transverse normal stresses in the core: The stresses in the core are also estimated within the framework of the analytical structural sandwich model proposed in [13]. The shear stress τ_c and the transverse normal stress σ_c are predicted to be constant through the core thickness.

The shear stress τ_c depends on the longitudinal coordinate x as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_c(x) &= \frac{Q(x)}{h_c + h_f} f_\tau \\ f_\tau &= 1 + \frac{D_f}{S} (c_1 \alpha_1^2 e^{-\alpha_1 x} + c_2 \beta_1^2 e^{-\beta_1 x}), \quad x > 0 \\ f_\tau &= 1 + \frac{D_f}{S} g^2 (c_3 \alpha_2^2 e^{+\alpha_2 x} + c_4 \beta_2^2 e^{+\beta_2 x}), \quad x < 0 \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

For the internal resultants acting as depicted in Fig. 1, the transverse normal stress is positive at the upper face-core interface and negative at the lower interface

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_c(x) &= \pm Q(x) \frac{h_c}{2(h_c + h_f)} f_z \\ f_z &= -\frac{D_f}{S} (c_1 \alpha_1^3 e^{-\alpha_1 x} + c_2 \beta_1^3 e^{-\beta_1 x}), \quad x > 0 \\ f_z &= +\frac{D_f}{S} g^2 (c_3 \alpha_2^3 e^{+\alpha_2 x} + c_4 \beta_2^3 e^{+\beta_2 x}), \quad x < 0 \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

The coefficients c_1, c_2, c_3, c_4 of the distribution (decay) functions f_σ and f_z in Eqs. (12) and (13) are found by solving the system of algebraic equations given by Eqs. (10).

Outside the zones of the local effects (i.e. outside the bending boundary layers) the shear and transverse normal stresses in the core in accordance with classical sandwich formulations [8]-[10] read:

$$\tau_c = \frac{Q(x)}{h_c + h_f}, \quad \sigma_c = 0 \quad (14)$$

NUMERICAL EXAMPLE

In order to demonstrate the applicability of the developed method of analysis, as well as to provide a more thorough understanding of the nature of the local stresses appearing in the vicinity of core junctions in sandwich panels, a numerical study has been carried out. In this study a sandwich beam is considered, and it is assumed that the shear stress resultant (shear force) is constant across the junction; $Q(x)=Q_0=1$ N/mm. The data of the sandwich beam used in the following numerical simulations and experiment study are given in Table 1. In Table 2 one finds shear moduli G_{c2} of the

stiff cores, which are to be used in the numerical simulations of various core joints, when $G_{c1}=22$ [MPa].

Table 1. Data of the sandwich beam: $g=0.435$, $\mu=0.681$.

	Thickness [mm]	Modulus of elasticity [MPa]	Shear modulus [MPa]	Poisson's ratio
Faces: Aluminium 2024-T6	1	$70 \cdot 10^3$	-	0.33
Compliant core: Divinycell® PVC H-60	20	60^a	$G_{c1}=22$	0.32
Stiff core: Divinycell® PVC H-200	20	310^a	$G_{c1}=116$	0.32

^a - compressive modulus [16]

Figure 2. Distribution of the local normal stresses in the face across the core junction for various core compositions.

Figure 3. Distribution of the local shear stresses in the core across the core junction for various core compositions. A sketch of the junction is given in Fig. 1. Shear modulus of the compliant core is $G_{c1}=22$ MPa, and the data of stiff cores are listed in Table 2.

Table 2. Data of the stiff cores (used in numerical simulations in Figs. 2 and 3).

	Shear modulus G_{c2} [Mpa]	Model parameter, g
PVC foam	44	0.707
Balsa core	220	0.316
Syntactic epoxy foam	2200	0.1
Rigid insert (steel)	$80 \cdot 10^3$	~ 0

The distributions of the local normal stress in the sandwich face, and the local core shear stress, are shown in Figs. 2 and 3, respectively. Here, the global resultant $Q_0=1 \text{ N/mm}$ is assumed to be constant in the vicinity of the junction. Four different ratios of $g=(G_{c1}/G_{c2})^{1/2}$ have been considered. On both figures a dashed line indicates the case of an infinitely stiff core, which is equivalent to the presence of a rigid insert with $G_{c2} \rightarrow \infty$.

The larger the difference between the elastic properties of the core is, the higher the additional normal stress in the faces will be (Fig. 2 and cf. Eq. (7)). The maximum possible normal stress appears at the edge of an infinitely rigid insert when $g=0$. The local shear stress (Fig. 3) in the core displays a substantial variation due to the severe local bending of the faces in a near vicinity of the junction. This variation increases with decreasing values of the ratio $g=(G_{c1}/G_{c2})^{1/2}$. The peak of local shear stress occurs some distance into stiffer core material. Notice that this peak is comparable with the values of the global shear stress $\tau_c=0.048 \text{ MPa}$ estimated via Eqs. (14). Then the total shear stress in the boundary layer is augmented in the stiff core and decreased in the compliant core (in the immediate vicinity of the junction).

It is worth to note that the behaviour of the local stresses is governed very much by the two parameters g and μ given by Eqs. (5) and (6). The first parameter g controls the magnitude of the local stresses. The severity of the local effects is most pronounced when core materials with properties that are very different are joined: $g \rightarrow 0$ (or $G_{c2}/G_{c1} \rightarrow \infty$), and the local effects vanish when cores of similar properties are joined: $g \rightarrow 1$ (or $G_{c2} \rightarrow G_{c1}$). The second model parameter μ is responsible for the spatial decay of the local effects. In Figs. 2 and 3 the local stresses are of insignificant magnitudes at distances of approximately one half of the core thickness away from the junction at $x=0$. The characteristic length of the local effects depends on the ratio of the core stiffness to the face stiffness defined by μ (see Eq. (6)). For the sandwich beam under consideration (Table 1) $\mu=0.68$. The extension zone of the local effects will decrease in magnitude for thinner and more compliant faces or for a thicker/stiffer core, i.e. when $\mu \rightarrow \infty$ then $k_\sigma \rightarrow 0$ in Eq. (7).

EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION OF THE MODEL

A symmetric sandwich beam loaded in three-point bending was chosen for validation of the analytical model. The beam was assembled with two different types of cores as shown in Figs. 4 and 5. The beam segments of stiff and compliant PVC core materials were bonded and furnished with aluminium faces through bonding with an epoxy adhesive. The width of the beam was $b=40 \text{ mm}$, and all other geometrical and mechanical parameters were as specified in Table 1. Notice that the force was applied far away from the adjacent core junctions, thus implying that the local effects induced by the load introduction or the points of support did not influence the local effects in the vicinity of the core junctions.

The loading of the beam was achieved with the help of a step motor (not shown in the Fig. 5), and the applied load was monitored by means of a calibrated force transducer. Measurements of the normal strains in the beam were performed with the help of single strain gauges situated far from the junctions, and strain gauge chains positioned across junction 2 (cf. Fig. 4).

Figure 4. A sandwich beam with two different cores in three-point bending. A coordinate of the beam span, that appears in Figs. 7-9 and 11, is indicated.

Figure 5. Experimental set-up for the investigation of local effects in the faces at the core junctions for the sandwich beam loaded in three-point bending.

Figure 6. Normal strains in the top face of the beam loaded in three-point bending with $F=600$ N: (a) Half of the beam is shown; (b) A zoom of junction 2. The theoretical estimates are shown by solid and dashed lines for the outer and inner surfaces of the top face, respectively. The experimental data are indicated by \circ and \times for the outer and inner surfaces, respectively.

The local effects were measured with the help of two strain gauge chains located at junction 2 (cf. Fig. 4). The zoom in Fig. 5 shows that one strain-gauge chain covered the junction along the outer surface of the top face, while a similar chain was glued parallel onto the inner surface of the same face. This arrangement enabled measurement of the strain distributions across the junction at both

sides of the top face. A correction of the measurements due to the thickness of the strain gauges and their glue substrates was included in the processing of the strain data. This was achieved by investigation and accurate thickness measurement of a cut in a similar assembly with the help of a microscope.

The face strains were measured both when the loading was applied, and when the beam was unloaded. The load was applied in turn to both faces of the sandwich beam. The deformation response was linear in the whole range of the applied loads: $F \in [0, 700 \text{ N}]$. The averaged experimental strains across the beam face together with the corresponding theoretical predictions are shown in Fig. 6 for $F=600 \text{ N}$, respectively. The solid lines represent the strain distributions along the outer (free) surface of the beam top face, and dashed lines represent the strains along the face-core interface. A somewhat larger deviation between the predicted and the measured strains was observed for the highest load and this may be explained by a higher sensitivity of the strain-gauges to material and adhesive layer imperfections, as well as by an enhanced influence of the boundary conditions for higher loads. However, the discrepancy between the experimental and the theoretical data is within the standard deviation of the experimental data.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS AND DESIGN ISSUES

The distribution of the stresses in the top face and in the core across junction 2 (situated at the distance of 130 mm from the left end of the beam) is shown in Fig. 7 for $F=600 \text{ N}$. A local face normal stress of $\sigma_0^{loc} = 43 \text{ MPa}$ (obtained via Eq. (7)) is present at the junction in addition to a globally induced bending stress of $\sigma_M^{top} = 45 \text{ MPa}$. Thus, the net bending stress increases to 92 MPa at the outer free surface of the sandwich face according to Eq. (11). At the same time the face normal stress at the face surface adjacent to the core almost vanishes, since it decreases to 2 MPa .

Figure 7. Normal stresses in the top face (outer and inner surfaces of the face), core transverse normal stresses σ_c and core shear stresses τ_c in the vicinity of beam junction 2 (see Fig. 4). The sandwich beam is loaded in three-point bending with $F=600 \text{ N}$.

If the local bending effects induced at the core junction were ignored, the maximum “global” bending stress of $\sigma_{max} = 66 \text{ MPa}$ (occurs at the sandwich beam mid-span) would appear to be the determining design stress. From the above it is clear that this would represent a serious underestimation of the actual stresses occurring in the sandwich beam.

The maximum transverse normal stress induced in the core is only $\sigma_c = 0.1 \text{ MPa}$ (neglecting here the local effects at the load introduction and the beam supports), whereas the maximum core shear stress achieves a value of $\tau_c = 0.45 \text{ MPa}$. However, taking into account that the shear strength of the core material Divinycell H-60 equals only 0.7 MPa [16], it appears that even this stress level may be dangerous for the structure under repetitive loading (fatigue). The associated shear at interfaces of

the core and faces can cause their detachment or initiate de-bonding that would lead to crack growth.

All of the foregoing analyses show that the larger the dissimilarity of properties of the adjacent cores, the higher the local bending stresses at the core junction. An obvious way to relieve these bending stresses in the faces is to reinforce them locally at the junctions. Another very practical way to diminish these stress concentrations is to introduce an additional segment of core (a patch core) with intermediate elastic properties, i.e. $G_{c1} < G_p < G_{c2}$. The consequence of introducing a core patch as shown in Fig. 8(a) is that instead of having just one junction causing severe local effects, two core junctions are obtained where the severity of the local effects is significantly reduced.

Figure 8. (a) - A junction is substituted by two sub-junctions via the introduction of an intermediate (patch) core of length 20 mm at junction 2. (b) - The normal stresses in the top face of sandwich beam as function of beam coordinate. Solid and dash lines represent the outer and inner surfaces of the face, respectively. The beam

(b)
(data - Table 1) is loaded in three-point bending with $F=600\text{ N}$

Fig. 8(b) displays the distribution of the face bending stresses in the top face across a core junction where a patch core of length 20 mm has been inserted. Two different patch cores are analysed in Fig. 8(b): one with a shear modulus of $G_p=70\text{ MPa}$, and one with $G_p=42\text{ MPa}$. For a sandwich beam configuration with a patch core with $G_p=70\text{ MPa}$ the maximum local bending stress at the first sub-junction is very high in comparison with the bending stress induced at the second sub-junction. For a sandwich beam configuration with a patch core with $G_p=42\text{ MPa}$ the local stresses at both sub-junctions equal 20 MPa, which is about half of the maximum local bending stresses induced if a stress relieving patch core is not used.

From the above simple example it is obvious that variation of the size and the elastic properties of a core patch can be used as a tool for “elastic tailoring”, i.e. to minimise the stress concentrations induced in the vicinity of a core junction in a particular sandwich structure, and thereby improving the overall structural performance.

CONCLUSIONS

A brief summary of the principles behind an advanced recently analytical model of the behaviour of symmetric sandwich beams and plates in cylindrical bending in the vicinity of core junctions has been given.

Closed-form analytical estimates of the local face and core stresses across core junctions, as well as the extension zones of the local effects have been presented. These may be used directly for preliminary design considerations of structural sandwich assemblies where different core materials are used.

The accuracy of the predictions of the proposed analytical model has been verified experimentally for the case of a sandwich beam with different core materials loaded in three-point bending. The severity of the local bending stresses in the faces of sandwich structures, where different cores are joined, may be reduced by reinforcement of the faces across the junctions. However, another more elegant approach to obtain the same stress relieving effect is to implement a gradual transition of the core stiffness from the stiffer to the more compliant core. A practical way of obtaining this would be to include one or more core patches with stiffness characteristics that are intermediate relative to the “stiff” and “compliant” core materials in the particular sandwich assembly considered.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The work presented has been cosponsored by the Danish Research Agency under the programme of “Materials Research”, “Novel Principles for Analysis and Design of Advanced Lightweight Composite and Sandwich Structures”, and the U.S. Navy, Office of Naval Research (ONR), Grant No. N0014001034, “Research on Advanced Composite Sandwich Constructions for Naval Surface Vessels: Analysis, Design and Optimization of Sandwich Shells”. The ONR supervisor was Dr. Yapa Rajapakse. The financial support received is gratefully acknowledged.

REFERENCES

1. The Handbook of Sandwich Construction. Zenkert D, ed. London: EMAS Publishing, 1997.
2. G. Holm, “Sandwich in marine structures – challenges and solutions for the structural designer”, *Proceedings of ICSS-4 Conference*. Stockholm, 1998.
3. A. Starlinger and U. Purtschert, “Hybrid design in mass transport vehicles – structural concept and analysis”, *Proceedings of ICSS-5 Conference*. Zurich, 2000.
4. G. H. Allen and F. Zhengnong, “Classification of structural sandwich panel behaviour”, *Proceedings of EUROMECH 360 Colloquium*. Saint-Étienne, 1997.
5. F. J. Plantema, “Sandwich Construction”, New York, John Wiley & Sons, 1966.
6. H. G. Allen, “Analysis and Design of Structural Sandwich Panels”, Oxford, Pergamon Press, 1969.
7. D. Zenkert, “An Introduction to Sandwich Construction”, London, EMAS Publishing, 1995.
8. Y. Frostig, “On stress concentration in the bending of sandwich beams with transversely flexible core”, *Comp. Struct.*, 24:161-169, (1993).
9. O. T. Thomsen, “Sandwich plates with “through-the-thickness” and “fully-potted” inserts: Evaluation of differences in structural performance”, *Comp. Struct.*, 40(2), 159-174 (1998).
10. O. T. Thomsen, “Analysis and design of sandwich plates with inserts a higher-order sandwich plate theory approach”, *Composites Part B*, 29B, 795-807 (1998).
11. O. T. Thomsen, “Localized bending effects in sandwich plates with inserts: A high-order approach for analysis and design”, *Proceedings of NESCO II Conference*. Stockholm, 1997.
12. V. Skvortsov, “Exact analysis of sandwich plates bending based on elasticity theory and the technique of integral transformation”, *Proceedings of ICSS-5 Conference*. Zurich, 2000.
13. V. Skvortsov and O. T. Thomsen, “Analytical estimates for the stresses in face sheets of sandwich panels at the junctions between different core materials”, *Proceedings of ICSS-6 Conference*. Fort Lauderdale, Florida, 2003.
14. A. K. Noor, W. S. Burton and C. W. Bert, “Computational models for sandwich panels and shells”, *Appl. Mech. Rev.*, 49 (1996).
15. V. Skvortsov, “Boundary effects and local stability of sandwich panels”, *Proceedings of EUROMECH 360 Colloquium Mechanics of Sandwich Structures*. Saint-Étienne, 1997.

16. Divinycell[®], DIAB. Technical Manual H-grade, 1995.